

**THE ESSENCE AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PROVIDING RISK-FREE
TOURISM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN****Gulyamov Kakhramon**

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The article analyzes tourism, its importance, specific features, development of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan, issues of ensuring security in this sector, and gives theoretical conclusions and recommendations related to the development of the sector.

Key words: tourism, security, safe tourism, Global , index , strategy, "Tax free", declaration, act, tourism, UNESCO, etc.

In the world The global trend of the 21st century - the role of tourism for the perspective of the individual, society and the state - continues to be connected with the increasing importance of creating a safe, inclusive and sustainable environment. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), the Global Peace Index ranks countries on a wide range of factors, from violence and crime rates to terrorism and international conflicts, according to which it is "the world's most peaceful place for 2023. " Iceland is the safest country in the first place, Denmark is in the next place due to the low level of corruption in the government, Ireland is in the third place, and the most dangerous countries that are not recommended for tourists are Afghanistan, Yemen, Syria, Iraq, Ukraine and Russia. "occupiers" ¹league is to ensure the personal safety of tourists in the world community, to protect their life, health, and property, to maintain public safety and order in tourism facilities, to eliminate obstacles that hinder the development of tourism, to ensure safe it shows that improvement of tourism provision is one of the urgent tasks.

In connection with ensuring security in the field of tourism in the world , the impact of criminal activity on tourism by M. Teixeira , the impact of terrorism on tourism by B. Rodrigues , organizational-legal, administrative and criminal aspects of administrative-legal provision of tourism security by ELPisarevskii researches have been conducted to reveal the problems . At the same time , maintaining public safety and order in tourism facilities, preventing violations and crimes in these areas, preventing social risks that tourists may become victims of forced

¹ Report of the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) // <https://www.timeout.com/news/the-safest-countries-in-the-world-have-been-announced-for-2023-070323> , [https://visitworld .today/blog/1539/most-dangerous-countries-in-the-world-in-2023-data-from-the-global-peace-index-rating](https://visitworld.today/blog/1539/most-dangerous-countries-in-the-world-in-2023-data-from-the-global-peace-index-rating) (Access time: 17.09.2023)

labor, human trafficking, research aimed at finding scientific solutions to the problems related to fraud and the development of safe factors for the organization of simplifying the arrival and departure of tourists is gaining urgent importance.

Systematic and comprehensive reforms aimed at increasing the attractiveness of existing historical and cultural objects in our country, ensuring the reliable safety of tourists coming and going to these objects, maintaining public order and security, preventing violations and fighting crime in this area are being implemented. In the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, "In order to develop the tourism sector, increase the number of foreign tourists to 15 million, the number of domestic tourists to 25 million, the number of tourists coming for pilgrimage tourism to 3 million, build 25 ropeways in mountainous areas, to increase the number of tourist centers to 175, to increase the export of tourism services to 5 billion dollars, to increase the export of medical and educational tourism to 1.5 billion dollars per year, to introduce the "Tax free" system for foreign tourists at all international airports for products purchased and cleared from the republic " ²The fact that specific measures have been established in connection with this issue makes it necessary to implement measures aimed at ensuring the safety of tourists' lives and property , and preventing various levels of damage to historical and cultural objects in our country .

set ourselves the goal of attracting up to 12 million foreign tourists to our country every year . Therefore, the attention of the government and governors should be focused on improving the infrastructure of the tourism industry, increasing the number of hotels, developing the transport network, and improving the quality of services ³. "

adopted by the World Tourism Organization on September 27, 2001, "The safety and protection of tourists should be a priority in each of the member countries of the World Tourism Organization, and any violence against tourists or tourism workers terrorist acts or attacks, kidnapping and threats, as well as the deliberate destruction of tourist objects and cultural-heritage objects should be prosecuted in accordance with the national legislation of each country ⁴.

At the same time, in the "Helsinki" final act adopted on August 1, 1975, "intercultural contacts and personal friendships that arise in the process of tourist exchange are an important

²Decree No. PF-158 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 " On the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030 " // National database of legislative information, <https://lex.uz>

³Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the joint meeting of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis on January 22 , 2020 .

⁴Seoul declaration "Mir and Tourism". Official site Vsemirnoy turistskoy organizatsii OON. URL: <http://www.unwto.org>

factor in ensuring international (global) security, and trust between the peoples of our planet and serves to create an atmosphere of mutual understanding ⁵.

In fact, in our opinion, it serves as an important factor in strengthening interstate friendly relations, further development of humanitarian criteria, and development of interpersonal and interethnic tolerance.

Francesco Frangialli stated that "tourism faces two main problems: the first is related to the present, that is, ensuring the safety of travel and eliminating crises; the second task is aimed at the long-term perspective and consists in choosing the way of tourism development. This will reduce its vulnerability, increase its sustainability and benefit the poorest local communities ⁶."

According to S.Tursunova, "Tourism's contribution to ensuring human security is to support the socio-economic development of countries and regions. The most important feature of ensuring security in tourist activity is the responsible management of the state based on the concept of development, the need to clearly see certain trends and changes in the future ⁷."

Security is a set of important conditions for ensuring the interests of the individual, society and the state. Ensuring security in a broad sense means ensuring personal, public and state security, protection of ecology, environment, historical and cultural objects, natural, man-made and social threats to the tourism sector, including administrative offenses, terrorism and protection against influences such as extremism.

To protect the rights and legal interests, life and health, and property of tourists, to provide high-quality and affordable services to foreign and local tourists, and at the same time to ensure the safety, rights, etc. of citizens while traveling, it is necessary to improve the measures aimed at creating effective mechanisms of all-round assistance in the realization of the freedoms of

It should be noted that modern science is paying more attention to the study of current issues of security every year. As a result of the development of research on security issues in the scientific literature, issues such as "Science in the field of security" (SVStepashin), as well as "Science in the field of human safety" (AATer-Akopov) are increasingly being raised ⁸.

⁵ Заключительный акт Soveshchaniya po bezopasnosti i sotrudnichestvu v Evrope. Helsinki, August 1, 1975. // Vedomosti VS USSR. 1980. No. 34. St. 690.

⁶Report on the 16th session of the General Assembly of the World Tourist Organization. Dakar (Senegal) November 28 - December 2, 2005. Official site Vsemirnoy turistskoy organizatsii OON. URL: <http://www.unwto.org>

⁷S.Tursunova, Improvement of administrative and legal measures to ensure safe tourism / Yu.ffd(PhD) disser. - T., JXU. 2023. -B. 156.

⁸Bobkova A.G., Kudrevatykh S.A., Pisarevsky E.L. Safety tourism. Uchebnik /.— M.: Federal agency for tourism, 2014. S. -13.

S. V. Stepashin stated that "the science of security includes ideological, general methodological principles of comprehensive security (security philosophy); interdependence of socio-economic and political conditions affecting security (sociology of security); legal regulation of security issues; it is necessary to reflect the use of mathematical modeling methods and a number of other problems to create comprehensive security models ⁹.

According to AIAndreevsky, "Certain conditions are necessary for a person's life, the development of his abilities and the possibility of achieving his human goals; among them safety and well-being are the most important. A state of security is ensured by preventing and suppressing threats from the evil will of other people, as well as natural forces and various accidents. A state of well-being is achieved by the ability to obtain and use a certain amount of material goods necessary to satisfy human needs. These two conditions - security and well-being are organically interrelated, and any measures that ensure security will contribute to the development of well-being and (or) be the opposite ¹⁰. In fact, the concepts of "tourism" and "security" are closely related to each other.

The history of tourism goes back a long way. In ancient Rome, travelers were offered a variety of paid services by a large number of guards, guides, and tour guides. They primarily ensured the safety of individuals and traveling groups. Then, they made the excursion, but due to the low level of preparation, they distorted the historical facts, and also behaved rudely and arrogantly while fighting for the client ¹¹.

of travelers, protection of their life and health from illegal attacks, as well as security of their property, provision of temporary housing and overnight accommodation are widespread in the traditions of various nations. Thus, the first procedures related to ensuring the safety of tourists go back to the history of Roman law. Roman law established the duty of hotels and hoteliers to ensure the safety of their guests as well as the safety of their property. According to the praetor's decree, the hotel owner automatically assumed responsibility for the safety of the guests' luggage. This responsibility ¹²is defined by the contract itself. Also, in order to create conditions for safe travel within the territory of the Roman Empire, a permanent military fleet was created. His detachments were located in the most important strategic places in the Mediterranean, as a result of which piracy was eliminated. Also, a uniform monetary system was

⁹ Stepashin S.V. Teoretiko-pravovye aspekti obespecheniya bezopasnosti Rossiyskoy Federatsii: avtoref. dis. walk to the doctor. science SPb., 1994. S. 39–40.

¹⁰ Andreevsky A.I. Police law. Volume I. — Spb.: typography Ed. Pratsa, 1871. S. 1 .

¹¹ Dulov A.N., Dyukhova K.A., Yurchak D.V.. Istoriya puteshestvii i turizma: monograph /– Vitebsk: UO «VGU im. P.M. Masherova», 2011. C - 50 .

¹² Chernilovsky Z.M. Lektsii po rimskomu chastnomu pravu. — M., 1991. S. 157

introduced everywhere, coins of different denominations and names were used: dinars, sesterces, etc., which were accepted for payment in the ancient Roman territories. Travelers, wherever they were, felt that Roman law was protected by a well-organized and regularly functioning judiciary¹³.

In ancient China, a number of reforms related to the provision of security and the development of social and economic sectors were implemented. For example, Emperor Shi Huangdi reformed under the motto "the road is the same length, all hieroglyphs are the standard script." At the same time, a single network of roads was created, the various hieroglyphic systems of the conquered kingdoms were abolished, a single monetary system, as well as a single system of weights and measures, were introduced. These measures helped promote trade and communication between different parts of the vast country. Strategic roads connected the capital with distant regions, the emperor himself made inspection trips along them. In order to protect the territory of his country, the emperor orders the construction of a wall in the north, which should protect China from the invasion of settlers. Covered with stone, fortified with towers and fortifications, the Great Wall of China (2,500 km long) was a huge structure built in little more than ten years¹⁴. The Great Wall of China is the most famous monument of ancient architecture. It receives up to 40 million tourists every year¹⁵.

The Byzantine emperor Justinian I in his Digests described the protection of the guests' property as follows: "The praetor says: If the sailors, innkeepers and landlords do not return what they have taken from someone under the condition of keeping the property, I will sue them. We say innkeeper or innkeeper, innkeeper or innkeeper, but a person who performs the duties of a servant, such as a porter, cook, porter, etc., cannot be innkeeper or innkeeper¹⁶."

In the Middle Ages, the strongest impetus for the development of tourism was given by pilgrims rushing to Christian and Muslim shrines. Wealthy Europeans loved to travel and relax in the resorts of Austria, Germany, Greece and Italy. The development of industry gave impetus to mass tourism. At that time, people began to be given paid vacations. In addition to all that has been said, mass tourism has given a great impetus to the development of roads and transport. Transportation such as water and railways (steamers and locomotives) began to appear. The first high-paying hotels appeared in Switzerland and Germany, and travel agencies were established

¹³Putrik Yu.S. Istoriya turizma: uchebnik / kolektiv avtorov;— M.: Federalnoe agentstvo po turizmu, 2014. S – 52.

¹⁴Putrik Yu.S. Istoriya turizma: uchebnik / collective author;— M.: Federalnoe agentstvo po turizmu, 2014. S – 37.

¹⁵ <https://podrobno.uz/cat/uzbekistan-i-kitay-klyuchi-ot-budushchego/stroyka-tsysyacheletiy-ezhednevno-velikuyu-kitayskuyu-#>. (Application time: 07.11.2022)

¹⁶Digesty Justiniana. Kniga chetvertaya. Title IX. M.: Statute. 2002. S. 46

in the second half of the 20th century. Travel agencies organize tours in Europe and sell them to consumers. At the same time, sports tourism and public recreation began to develop in Germany . 40 The military actions of the 1990s brought unique changes in the development of European tourism . 50 of the XX century A new stage of development began in the 1990s, by this time tourism companies had multiplied , and mass construction of hotels and entertainment facilities had begun. In the 80s, tourism became a way of life for people. The types of services have expanded, and new types of tourism such as individual tours and ecological tourism have begun to ¹⁷appear .

"With the development of technology and industrialization at the end of the 19th and 20th centuries, the category of "security" became an attribute of not only state but also private law. Personal injury cases caused by machines and mechanisms are common in France. In this regard, a new legal concept appears - " *obligation de securite* " . Since the 1880s, the issue of compensation for such damage caused during the performance of the contract has been raised in French legal literature ¹⁸.

Industrial tourism began to appear from this period. Recently, the interest of tourists in industrial heritage objects is increasing. The establishment of international organizations such as the International Committee for the Preservation of Industrial Heritage, the Society of Industrial [Archeology and the Association of Industrial Archeology](#) shows that the field of ensuring the safety of these tourist objects is also developing.

The most preferred destinations for industrial tourism are cities and regions with a strong industrial base, especially in Western Europe. A similar trend began to appear in the countries of Central Europe. ¹⁹Great tourist interest is shown in non-existent enterprises that have become history, sometimes included in UNESCO sites. An important condition for the potential of industrial tourism is the location of objects (transportation, infrastructure, environment), access to attractions (costs, services, qualified guides), availability of information about the object (marketing and advertising). ²⁰. Development of industrial tourism in our country as a type of tourism , at the same time establishing a system of ensuring the safety of tourists in industrial facilities, will contribute to increasing the tourism potential of our republic and increasing its reputation as a safe country. In our opinion, the comprehensive reforms in the field of industrial

¹⁷ <https://sportsfan.ru/sports-academy/summer-sports/tourism/history-tourism.html> .

¹⁸Bobkova A.G., Kudrevatykh S.A., Pisarevsky E.L. Safety tourism. Uchebnik /.— M .: Federalnoe agency po tourism , 2014. S 19 .

¹⁹ [The Industrial History and Identity of Central and South Eastern Europe](http://www.visitfactories.com/attractions.php) <http://www.visitfactories.com/attractions.php> . (Application time: 02.11.2023)

²⁰ <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki> (Access time: 02. 0 1.202 4)

development in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the establishment of reliable friendship relations with neighboring countries and developed countries in the field of industrial development, are important factors for the development of tourism in this field. serves as

Based on the above, the following theoretical conclusions can be made:

firstly, it serves as an important factor in strengthening interstate friendly relations, further development of humanitarian criteria, and development of interpersonal and interethnic tolerance;

secondly, security is an important set of conditions for ensuring the interests of the individual, society and the state. Ensuring security in a broad sense means ensuring personal, public and state security, protection of ecology, environment, historical and cultural objects, natural, man-made and social threats to the tourism sector, including administrative offenses, terrorism and explained by protection against influences such as extremism;

thirdly, to protect the rights and legal interests, life and health, and property of tourists, to organize the provision of high-quality and affordable services to foreign and domestic tourists, and at the same time to ensure the safety and rights of citizens when traveling, etc. , it is necessary to improve the measures aimed at creating effective mechanisms of all-round assistance in the realization of their freedoms;

fourthly, the comprehensive reforms in the field of industrial development in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the establishment of reliable friendship relations with neighboring countries and developed countries in the field of industrial development, are an important factor for the development of tourism in this field. serves as